

Code-to-Code Validation of LFR Pin Cells Burnup Calculations with DRAGON5

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ABSTRACT

The time-dependent evolution of the fuel inventory due to irradiation and radioactive decay is crucial for reactor design. This study evaluates the capability of the deterministic lattice code DRAGON to perform depletion calculations for lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs) through comparison with the Monte Carlo code OpenMC. Calculation parameters and schemes were chosen to balance accuracy and computational cost and tailored fine-group nuclear data libraries with enhanced energy resolution were generated. DRAGON results showed a good agreement with OpenMC, with a maximum deviation of 170 pcm in the multiplication factor at end of life, and maximum relative discrepancy of the order of 0.1% and 0.5% in the number densities of most actinides and fission products respectively, while retaining relatively small computational effort. Calculations with well-known deterministic code ERANOS were shown to give similar accuracy for the multiplication factor but higher discrepancy in number densities. These results demonstrate that DRAGON can reliably perform depletion calculations in fast reactors when supported by carefully designed data libraries - including decay chains, fission yields, and energy deposition information - and calculation schemes.

Keywords: Burnup calculations, LFR, DRAGON

1. INTRODUCTION

In nuclear reactors, the fuel, coolant and structural materials are subject to irradiation during long periods of time. Because of the irradiation, nuclides undergo transmutation, leading to a change in composition that must be taken into account in neutron transport calculations. This time-dependent process is known as isotopic depletion. Accurate estimates of changes in reactivity and fuel composition due to depletion are essential for designing new reactors, such as *newcleo's* lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs).

Depletion is described by the Bateman equation which is solved by most neutron transport lattice codes. An open-source deterministic code of choice is DRAGON (Version5.1), which has been developed at Polytechnique Montréal [1] with the aim of offering a variety of schemes for self-shielding and transport solutions. DRAGON includes the EVO: module that performs burnup calculations.

DRAGON was developed for thermal reactor applications. Therefore, its results need to be validated for fast reactor applications, paying special attention to nuclear data libraries used, which include decay chains, fission yields and information on energy deposition in fission. In this paper results of DRAGON are compared with results from OpenMC 0.15.1, an open-source Monte Carlo code [2]. Additionally, DRAGON's performance among deterministic approaches is assessed against the consolidated deterministic code ERANOS 2.3 N[3]. In Sec. 2, the theory of depletion is revised and its implementation in DRAGON and OpenMC is explained. Sec. 3. describes library production for depletion with DRAGON, the calculational schemes used and in Sec. 4, decay chains and fission yields in DRAGON are verified. Finally, results are shown in Sec. 5 and conclusions are offered in Sec. 6.

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2. DEPLETION CALCULATIONS

2.1. The Bateman equation

In a given mixture containing K isotopes, concentrations of different isotopes $N_k(t)$ satisfy the Bateman equations

$$\frac{dN_k(t)}{dt} + N_k(t) \Lambda_k(t) = S_k(t) \quad \text{for } k = 1, \dots, K \quad (1)$$

with the removal coefficient $\Lambda_k(t) = \lambda_k + \langle \sigma_{a,k}(t) \phi(t) \rangle$ where λ_k is the radioactive decay constant for the k -th isotope, $\sigma_{a,k}(t)$ is the time-dependent microscopic cross section for absorption and $\phi(t, E)$ is the time- and energy-dependent scalar neutron flux in the mixture. Furthermore, the production term $S_k(t)$ in Equation (1) is

$$S_k(t) = \sum_{l=1}^K [f_{k \leftarrow l} \langle \sigma_{r,l}(t) \phi(t) \rangle + m_{k \leftarrow l}(t)] N_l(t) \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_{r,l}(t)$ is the transmutation microscopic cross section for nuclide l , $f_{k \leftarrow l}$ is the fraction of transmutation reactions in nuclide l that produce nuclide k (in the case of fission, it represents the fission yield for the production of fission product k by fissile isotope l), and $m_{k \leftarrow l}(t)$ the radioactive decay constant for production of isotope k by isotope l . For a generic reaction r , $\langle \sigma_{r,k} \phi(t) \rangle = \int dE \sigma_{r,k}(E) \phi(t, E)$.

Depletion calculations can be performed at constant flux or constant power. In this work, all calculations were carried out at fixed power density, as this option better reflects the operating conditions of the fuel elements in a nuclear reactor. In fact, a reactor normally runs at the design thermal power, where its performance is optimized. In this case, the power released per mass of initial heavy element at beginning-of-life and end-of-life is set to a constant value W .

2.2. Implementation of depletion in DRAGON and OpenMC

DRAGON burnup calculations are performed with the `EV0:` module [1]. In a typical calculation, the neutron flux distribution is first obtained for a given initial nuclide concentration in fresh fuel through the flux calculation module (`FLU:`). This flux is then used to calculate transmutation rates, which are passed to the depletion module (`EV0:`) to update the isotopic inventory. The updated inventory is in turn used to update the flux, with consecutive transport and depletion calculations. In the `EV0:` module, the depletion equations are solved using the burnup chains present in the nuclear data library. In this work, the lumped depletion matrix system containing the non-saturating isotopes is solved using a fourth order Kaps-Rentrop algorithm [4], but it should be noticed that DRAGON also offers other numerical solvers.

At each step of burnup, the flux and reaction rates are normalized in DRAGON to keep the power constant. The contribution of fission to energy deposition was calculated as

$$\sum_g Q_{f,k,g} \sigma_{f,k,g} \phi_g \quad (3)$$

where the groups g are summed over. Q_f is the pseudo- Q value of the fission event, i.e. the kinetic energy of fission products, neutrons (both prompt and delayed), photons (both prompt and delayed) and beta particles, but not that of neutrinos. The pseudo- Q value is assumed to be independent of the incident neutron energy and is taken directly from evaluated nuclear data libraries.¹ Energy deposition

¹The latest version, DRAGON5.1, alternatively allows to evaluate energy deposition by using KERMA factors, provided that they were computed through the NJOY module HEATR and stored in the nuclear data library.

from, e.g., (n, γ) and (n, xn) events was also included through a Q -value but elastic scattering was neglected, as its Q -value is zero. We therefore assumed that the kinetic energy of neutrons is released at the fission site.

The Monte Carlo code OpenMC was used to assess the accuracy of DRAGON results. OpenMC supports depletion calculations through the `openmc.deplete` Python module and can perform transport-coupled depletion by combining the module with a transport solver. The depletion module provides several time-integration methods for computing the evolution of material compositions. In the present calculations, a CE/LI Predictor-Corrector algorithm was adopted, see [2] for further details.

Understanding the normalization of the flux and reaction rates is crucial when comparing different codes. OpenMC relies on so-called KERMA (Kinetic Energy Release in Materials) where the total heat deposited at the collision site is calculated by multiplying the cross section and the sum of the energies of the recoiling nucleus and other products. OpenMC separates the total KERMA into fission and non-fission components, so that

$$h_i(E) = h_{i,nf}(E) + [Q_f - Q_{n,p} - Q_{n,d}]\sigma_{i,f}(E), \quad (4)$$

where Q_f is the total energy released in a fission event, ignoring the energy carried away by neutrinos. This approach is implemented in OpenMC through the so-called *energy-deposition* mode, that computes the total deposited energy and uses the ratio of the power to the energy produced as a normalization factor [2]. This option was adopted in the present work. Only neutron transport was considered, so that the energy of prompt and delayed photons is deposited locally, while the energies of both prompt and delayed neutrons, $Q_{n,p}$ and $Q_{n,d}$, are subtracted.

3. SETUP OF BURNUP CALCULATIONS IN DRAGON

The simulation domain was an infinite lattice of hexagonal pin cells, representative of *newcleo's* LFR-AS-200 reactor. It is composed, moving radially outward, of a helium hollow, MOX fuel, a helium gap, and AIM1 steel cladding. Lead coolant circulates in the outermost space between the cladding and the cell boundary (see Figure 1). The fuel is a mixed uranium-plutonium oxide (MOX).

Figure 1. Hexagonal Cell geometry.

DRAGON provides several methods for the solution of the Boltzmann neutron transport equation, including the collision probability method (CPM), the method of characteristics (MOC) and the interface current (IC) method. These solution methods use P0-corrected scattering by default, but true PN scattering is possible with MOC. In this study, the CPM is used for the self-shielding calculation and the MOC with P0-corrected scattering is used for the main flux calculation. The energy domain is discretized into a fine structure of 1962 groups, and the spatial domain is analyzed by the EXCELT: tracking module. Isotropic tracking parameters are associated with white boundary conditions (i.e., isotropic reflection) and used to implement the collision probability method (CPM), while specular (cyclic) tracking is used along with reflective boundary conditions for the method of characteristics (MOC). Such a setup was observed to improve performance. Self-shielding is calculated using Tone's method [5], implemented in the TONE: module, chosen for its simplicity and good performance with fine energy discretization. Comparisons with other self-shielding modules, such as the USS: module based on the

subgroup method, showed only negligible discrepancies and similar computation times. The depletion calculation was run considering eleven timesteps, expressed in effective full power days (EFPDs) as 0, 5, 30, 180, 480, 765, 1020, 1275, 1575, 1875, and 2040. The time steps were chosen as a compromise between computational effort and accuracy of results.

3.1. Production of libraries for DRAGON

DRAGON calculations require libraries in the so-called DRAGLIB format, with cross sections in a certain group structure. These libraries are generated through NJOY-2016 supplemented by the DRAGR module. Preliminary comparisons of DRAGON against OpenMC for the pin cell with fresh fuel have shown that accurate results (within a few tens of pcm for k_∞) can be obtained using libraries with a fine energy-group structure, i.e. 1962 energy groups. In burnup calculations, the library must contain detailed information for a large number of isotopes, which makes nuclear data libraries generally quite large. A major contribution to the library size comes from the scattering transfer matrices, which have size $n_g \times n_g$, with n_g the number of energy groups.

The DRAGR module allows one to control the level of detail in transfer matrices in libraries for a given isotope through the fp parameter. For an isotope with $fp = 0$ the full transfer matrix is included, while with $fp = 1$ the matrix is set to be diagonal, meaning that neutrons remain in the same energy group after scattering off the isotope. To balance accuracy and library size, a decay chain with 300 isotopes was used, and isotopes were ranked according to their contribution to the total macroscopic scattering cross section in an LFR fuel pin cell. The 100 isotopes with the highest contributions were assigned $fp = 0$, while the others were assigned $fp = 1$. To check this new library with mixed fp treatment, it was compared against a library which contained only isotopes found in fresh fuel and which had a full transfer description for all of them. The resulting multiplication factors differed by only 10 pcm between the two libraries. This shows that using the new library, burnup calculations with a fine energy mesh are accessible at the cost of only a small loss in accuracy.

3.2. Setup of calculational scheme in DRAGON

An important factor to consider in burnup calculations is the computation time, which can become significant even for a deterministic code due to the large number of energy groups and depleting isotopes involved. Some strategies have therefore been implemented in the DRAGON calculation scheme to speed up burnup calculations.

One way to accelerate burnup calculations in DRAGON is through OpenMP parallelization which acts on DRAGON's tracking module. By using OpenMP, different tracks and energy groups can be processed simultaneously across multiple cores, leading to significant performance improvements. For the fuel pin cell in Figure 1 with 1962 energy groups, OpenMP parallelization resulted in a 25% reduction in computation time on 16 threads with 300 tracks processed by each core. OpenMP parallelization was adopted throughout the simulations presented below.

A trade-off between accuracy and computation time was also investigated by comparing two calculation schemes. The first scheme performs two depletion and transport calculations per time step. The size of the step is denoted by Δt and the time at the beginning of the step by t_0 . As shown in Figure 2, the concentrations are first updated using the flux at t_0 , followed by a transport calculation for an approximate flux. This flux is then used as a feedback to a second depletion calculation, before performing a final transport calculation to obtain the flux at $t_0 + \Delta t$. The second scheme, in contrast, performs only a single depletion and transport calculation per step, without any feedback. As expected, the first scheme is more time-consuming, increasing runtime by 35% compared to the second scheme. However, both schemes produce essentially identical results, with discrepancies limited to a few fractions of pcm. The single-transport scheme was therefore adopted for subsequent calculations.

Another aspect that directly impacts both accuracy and computation time is the number of self-shielding

Figure 2. Calculation scheme with two depletion and transport calculations per time step.

calculations performed during evolution, which is often the most time-consuming component in burnup calculations. Only fissile isotopes in the fuel, lead isotopes in the coolant and ^{56}Fe in the cladding were self-shielded as self-shielding more isotopes increases the computation time while only increasing accuracy by a few pcm. Since fuel composition changes in time, the relative importance of isotopes' resonances in cross section can undergo changes as well. Three calculation schemes were tested, where self-shielding is calculated a) at every burnup step, b) every other step, and c) only at the first step. In the last two schemes, self-shielded microscopic cross sections from earlier time steps are used when self-shielding is not performed. Table I summarizes results in terms of multiplication factor and computation time. $|\overline{\Delta k}|$ represents the average deviation of the multiplication factor relative to the reference, while $|\Delta k_{\max}|$ denotes the maximum deviation. One has

$$|\overline{\Delta k}| = \frac{1}{N_{\text{step}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{step}}} |k_i - k_{\text{ref},i}| \quad \text{and} \quad |\Delta k_{\max}| = \max(|k_i - k_{\text{ref},i}|) \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, N_{\text{step}}. \quad (5)$$

A reduction in computation time by 44% was achieved on 16 threads by calculating self-shielding every other step, with maximum 15 pcm discrepancy in the multiplication factor. For a pin cell calculation, the overhead constitutes a significant portion of the total computation time, which explains why only a modest time improvement is observed between options b) and c). A more significant speedup is instead expected at the assembly level, where the overhead contribution is comparatively smaller.

Table I. Comparison of multiplication factor and computation time for DRAGON pin-cell burnup simulations with different self-shielding calculation schemes. Option a) is taken as reference.

Self-shielding calculated	$ \overline{\Delta k} $ (pcm)	$ \Delta k_{\max} $ (pcm)	Computation time (min)	Gain in time (%)
a) at each time step (Reference)	-	-	25	-
b) every other step	6.5	15	14	44%
c) at the first time step only	25.4	42	11	56%

4. VERIFICATION OF DECAY CHAINS AND FISSION YIELDS

In order to ensure the consistency of the results obtained with OpenMC and DRAGON, a dedicated verification of decay chains and fission yields has been performed. OpenMC provides both complete and simplified chains. Officially, two complete chains are distributed: one tailored to a thermal spectrum (LWR) and one representative of a fast spectrum (SFR). Both are generated from ENDF/B-VIII.0 sublibraries (incident neutron, decay, and fission yields) and differ mainly in the adopted capture branching ratios, which are spectrum-dependent. In addition, OpenMC offers two simplified chains—again for thermal and fast spectra—based on a reduced set of isotopes recommended by the VERA depletion benchmark specification. These simplified versions retain only the most relevant actinides and fission products, for a total of 255 nuclides, including 42 actinides and 150 fission products. In the present work, the fast spectrum decay chains libraries were employed in the OpenMC calculations [6]. DRAGON, by contrast, relies exclusively on a reduced chain representation, with the library used in this paper including 31 actinides and 172 fission products. A similar structure is adopted in ERANOS, which has been

configured using an ENDF/B-VIII.0 ECCO library and a depletion chain comprising 23 fissile isotopes and 87 fission products.

Figure 3. Fission yield comparison for ^{99}Tc .

Figure 4. Fission yield comparison for ^{101}Ru .

The comparison between DRAGON and OpenMC was carried out using the simplified OpenMC chain, since it is directly derived from the complete one and thus provides a consistent basis for validation. The comparison between the two chains has been based primarily on the analysis of fission yields Y_{kl} , as defined in Equation 2, focusing on the fission products present in the largest quantities. It is important to distinguish between independent fission yields (IFYs), defined as the number of atoms of a given nuclide produced directly in the fission process without accounting for any subsequent decay, and cumulative fission yields (CFYs), which include both the direct production and the contributions arising from the decay of all precursor nuclides. In the framework of simplified depletion chains, this distinction becomes particularly critical: several short-lived precursors are lumped or omitted, and their production pathways are therefore not explicitly tracked but rather taken into account effectively through CFYs. For this reason, a direct comparison with the complete chain is less straightforward: since the longer chain explicitly contains information in terms of independent fission yields (IFYs), a consistent comparison would require the reconstruction of the corresponding cumulative yields (CFYs) by accounting for the decay of all precursor nuclides.

Among the fission products contributing more than 0.4% to the total absorption, almost all show only small differences between OpenMC and DRAGON. This is exemplified by ^{101}Ru in Figure 4, for which the largest discrepancy is about 0.14% in the case of ^{235}U . Among the main fission products, ^{99}Tc is the only nuclide exhibiting more pronounced discrepancies, with a difference of approximately 19% for ^{242}Pu but a much smaller difference for all other actinides, see Figure 3. These results confirm the reliability of the fission yield data in DRAGON.

5. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the comparison between DRAGON, ERANOS and OpenMC. All three codes simulate the fuel pin cell in Figure 1. The DRAGON results are for the calculation scheme in which self-shielding is performed at every step. The ERANOS depletion calculation was performed using ECCO as a transport solver [3], and performing a self-shielding calculation at each burnup step. Energy deposition was evaluated by summing the Q-values of fission and capture reactions included in the ECCO library, and subtracting a term that accounts for energy loss in scattering.

The left hand side of Figure 5 shows the reactivity-vs-burnup curves obtained with DRAGON, ERANOS

Figure 5. Comparison of DRAGON and ERANOS with OpenMC on reactivity vs burnup behaviour. Abbreviations in the legend: sc = simplified chain; fc = full chain; $\Delta k = k_{E/D} - k_{OpenMC}$; D = DRAGON; E = ERANOS.

and OpenMC, considering both the full and simplified decay chains, while the right hand side shows discrepancies in k_{∞} . Overall, there is good agreement, with a maximum difference of about 170 pcm for DRAGON and 155 pcm for ERANOS at end of life (EoL). Both deterministic codes match the simplified chain more closely, consistently with the findings of Section 4, where DRAGON and the OpenMC simplified chains exhibited similar behaviour while still presenting some differences. Table II shows the reactivity swing obtained by the three codes throughout the reactor life. It shows very good agreement between DRAGON and ERANOS, with both results falling between the two OpenMC chains.

Table II. Reactivity swing in Dragon, ERANOS, and OpenMC for final burnup of 74 MWd/kg.

	DRAGON	ERANOS	OpenMC with simplified chain	OpenMC with full chain
Reactivity swing (pcm)	5959	5950	5913	6074

Table III reports relative errors on number densities at EoL for both deterministic codes, computed as

$$\epsilon = \frac{N_{\text{DRAGON/ERANOS}} - N_{\text{OpenMC}}}{N_{\text{OpenMC}}} \times 100\%. \quad (6)$$

The reported values refer to the comparison with the full decay chain in OpenMC. For DRAGON, errors remain around or below 0.1% for most fissile isotopes and around 0.5% for fission products. The exception are higher error on Pu238 due to the branching fractions for the (n, γ) reaction off Am241 leading to Am242, whose decay quickly produces Pu238, and to its metastable state Am242m. These branching fractions are energy-dependent, and the DRAGLIB includes thermal energy data by default. This aspect will be further explored in future work. For ERANOS, errors are consistently larger for fission products than for actinides, reaching up to 14.6% and 0.35%, respectively. The relatively large errors in ERANOS for fission products are due to a high discrepancy in its fission yields. Due to their deterministic approach, DRAGON and ERANOS are much more computationally efficient than OpenMC, with pin-cell simulations completing in roughly 25 and 15 minutes respectively, compared to 25 hours for OpenMC.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work assessed the capability of the deterministic code DRAGON to perform depletion calculations for a representative case of LFRs. Different calculation schemes in DRAGON were tested to optimize accuracy and computational efficiency. Dedicated fine-group nuclear data libraries were generated,

Table III. Relative error on nuclides densities at EoL between both DRAGON and ERANOS, and OpenMC with full decay chain.

Relative error	²³⁸ U	²³⁹ Pu	²⁴¹ Pu	²⁴⁰ Pu	²³⁸ Pu	²⁴² Pu	²⁴¹ Am	¹⁰⁵ Pd	⁹⁹ Tc	¹⁰¹ Ru
DRAGON	0.06%	0.02%	-0.03%	-0.06%	0.68%	0.09%	0.37%	-0.55%	-0.54%	-0.54%
ERANOS	-0.007%	0.07%	-0.06%	-0.10%	-0.24%	-0.35%	0.11%	-3.10%	-14.6%	7.78%

structured to provide more information on the scattering transfer matrix for the most relevant nuclides. Furthermore, decay chains and fission yields were studied, showing overall consistency between DRAGON and the simplified decay chain of the Monte Carlo code OpenMC.

Results for burnup calculations with DRAGON showed good agreement with OpenMC results, with a maximum discrepancy of 170 pcm in multiplication factor at EoL and relative error in the number densities of most fissile isotopes and fission products on the order of 0.1% and 0.5% respectively. Slightly higher discrepancies for Pu238 and Am241 will be the topic of further studies. A comparison with the well-known deterministic code ERANOS indicated that both deterministic codes exhibit similar performance in calculations of reactivity as a function of burnup, and in the isotopic number density of actinides, but DRAGON gave better agreement in number densities of fission products.

Overall, this study demonstrated the strong potential of performing depletion calculations for LFRs with DRAGON, when supported by nuclear data libraries specifically developed for fast reactors and an appropriately designed calculation scheme. Future work will focus on investigating the remaining discrepancies to better understand their origin and improve predictive accuracy. New DRAGON libraries, including KERMA factors generated by HEATR, will be validated soon. Additionally, the development of calculation schemes for larger and more complex geometries will be pursued, a feature further supported by the integration with the GLOW² package, developed at *newcleo*. This capability is particularly valuable for assembly- and core-level calculations, enabling spatially detailed analyses and further enhancing the applicability of DRAGON for fast reactor depletion studies.

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²<https://github.com/newcleo-dev-team/glow>.